

Rethinking Mathematical Bridging Courses

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Abstract

Mathematical bridging courses offered prior to the beginning of the first semester are often designed in Germany with the goal being to get students all at the same level of knowledge, as a way for students to fill the gaps in their school mathematics. This lofty goal has been shown to be highly unrealistic. In general, it seems that the students who need these courses the least are more likely to attend in comparison to those who need these courses. The gap between students' abilities seems to become larger, which shows that the needs of diverse groups are not suitably addressed with this format.

In this contribution, we look at some of the reasons why bridging courses fail to alleviate the problems that they were designed to create. Some different approaches to redesigning bridging courses are given along with some observations concerning their effectiveness.

Keywords: Bridging courses, activating students, individualisation

Introduction

Offering mathematical bridging courses is a way to prepare students for their mathematics courses at the college level. In the German system, this type of course, aimed at beginning engineering students, is often a compressed review of mathematics taught at school. One of the main goals is to fill in the gaps in order to attain some sort of homogeneity in terms of the abilities of the students so that instructors of college courses can rely on students having the prerequisite knowledge and skills. [see e.g. 1, 2] This was also the case, at least part of the time, in the different universities where the author has been working over the past 20 years. Unfortunately, the classroom situation in first semester mathematics courses shows that this goal is often unmet. It seems as if the students who were good in mathematics in school gain the most from the mathematical bridging course, which in turn only widens the gap between student abilities.

In this contribution, some observations made at the Technische Universität Berlin (TUB), the Technische Hochschule Ostwestfalen-Lippe (TH OWL), and the Technische Hochschule Ingolstadt (THI) will be examined to make some suggestions for revamping these courses.

Mathematical Bridging Courses

Clearly not all bridging courses are the same. Most of the focus in this article will be on the in-person courses that review school mathematics with some insights concerning online refresher courses. The main evaluation of student success in relation to bridging

courses was conducted at the TUB in the year 2009 [3, pp. 15-20, 152-157]. During that time, there was an in-person presence bridging course, an online bridging course, and a so-called Early Bird course. The latter course invited talented students to complete the first semester analysis and linear algebra courses before the first semester began. Thus, any student included in the survey who attended Early Bird had either not passed the examination in linear algebra prior to beginning the first semester or they were unsatisfied with their grade. The comparison of this course to the others may be unfair because the goals are different. It is included for reflection purposes.

The scope of each course was as follows. The introductory course was a 2-week in-person course. Students went to a daily lecture and a daily tutorial with the content matching a subset of the online bridging course. The online bridging course was quite lengthy. There was no recommended timeline for this course. Early Bird was a two-month course with a daily lecture and exercise session.

Students were asked to indicate which type of course(s) they attended: in-person, online, Early Bird, none. Of the 1361 students responding, the percentage of students attending a particular form were nearly the same for men (1087 participants) and women (274 participants). Taken together, 42% of the students attended the bridging course in-person, 46% online, 6% Early Bird, 35% none. We see that some students used more than one offering simultaneously. With these different formats, we were able to reach nearly 2/3 of our students.

The same students were asked to estimate how much of the course they had attended: up to $\frac{1}{4}$, more than $\frac{1}{4}$ up to $\frac{1}{2}$, more than $\frac{1}{2}$ up to $\frac{3}{4}$, and more than $\frac{3}{4}$. Again, the responses of men and of women were very similar. Whereas 47% of the students in the introductory course stayed past the $\frac{3}{4}$ mark, 62% of the Early Bird participants remained as long. Since the online course is rather lengthy, only 12% claimed to have finished at least $\frac{3}{4}$ of the course. Whether the students were demotivated by the length of the online course is not clear from the data. All in all, we can say that the average student attending the bridging course completed about 63% of the course. For the online course this figure was about 40% and for Early Bird 65%. Thus, both in-person courses were similar in terms of the amount attended by the participants. The amount of the bridging course attended was not dependent on whether the student had taken an advanced course in mathematics during high school or not: bridging course (63% vs. 65%), online course (42% vs. 41%). Not surprisingly this was not the case for Early Bird (71% vs. 58%).

In an attempt to understand the effect bridging courses play, we will compare the results of students attending the first-semester course “Linear Algebra for Engineers” at the TUB in the winter semester of 2009/2010. Although the results are from 15 years ago, the message is still valid.

A key to success in this course was, as expected, previous experience at school. The following table shows the percentage of students successfully completing the course based on participation in an advanced course in mathematics at the school level and the amount of the bridging course attended.

School math	51-100%	1-50%	0% of bridging course
Advanced course	59%	53%	42%
General math only	41%	33%	27%

Another factor that influenced performance was whether a student liked mathematics. The next table illustrates the percentage of students successfully completing the course taking into account whether the student likes mathematics and if a bridging course was attended or not.

Attitude Towards Mathematics	Bridging Course	No Bridging Course
Like mathematics	57%	42%
Indifferent to mathematics	33%	31%
Do not like mathematics	21%	20%

Students who said they really enjoy mathematics and attended a preparatory course successfully completed the course at a 15% higher rate than those not attending. Students who said they were indifferent to or did not enjoy mathematics successfully completed the course at about the same rate regardless of whether they took part in a bridging course.

Relating performance and self-estimated abilities in mathematics based on participation in a bridging course shows a bigger differentiation than liking mathematics. The following table shows the success rates in the course.

Estimated Abilities in Math	Bridging Course	No Bridging Course
Above average	63%	52%
Average	41%	29%
Below average	20%	21%

These findings raise the question of whether bridging courses are really the appropriate way to prepare students who estimate their abilities as below average and/or do not like mathematics for their college-level mathematics courses.

At the TH OWL's Höxter campus we observed the bridging course in 2015. It was a two-week course offered in the morning in-person. Notes were taken as to the interactions between the instructor, who was a retired mathematics teacher from a local high school, the tutor, and the participants. Due to the small sample size of 24, the results are not representative. The observations are thus summarized qualitatively. The students who demonstrated more knowledge tended to continue until the end. The instructor interacted with these students considerably more frequently than with the students who demonstrated that they did not understand. Those who did not understand for more than one day tended to not return. This experience reinforced some of the findings at the TUB. It was clear that a bridging course needs to be more individualized to meet the needs of the actual target audience.

The THI also offers a review of school mathematics in its two-week bridging course before the first semester of studies. The experiences of the instructor parallels those recorded above. There is low attendance in terms of the number of incoming students in technical disciplines needing mathematics. Traditionally, about 70%-80% of the students enrolled in the in-person course remain at the end of the two weeks. Some of the main reasons for students not attending the bridging course were that students were unaware of the course, students did not feel the contents were important or relevant for their studies, and/or students were physically unable to attend.

The project THI-Success^{AI} (funded by the foundation "Stiftung Innovation in der Hochschullehre", project identification FBM2020-EA-1690-07540) aims to combine AI with the learning process. Two of the main features of this Moodle-based platform, which was conceived for supporting students in the self-learning phase, will be a recommendation system, which puts together individual learning paths for students based on their previous history, and a learning companion, which allows students to network with each other or a peer mentor to discuss a specific learning activity. These features are expected to be helpful for students to learn and discuss mathematics (online) at their own level. Course contents have been created for two semesters in the areas of mathematics, statistics, programming and electrical engineering.

This platform is currently being extended to offer a different kind of bridging course concurrent with the mathematics taught in the first semester (here, calculus). The idea is to distribute the topics of school mathematics over the course of the semester with the featured skills of the week being used in the next lecture. This shows the use of the skill in context, adding to the feeling of usefulness of the skill. The reminder of the skill directly before its use theoretically enhances the assimilation process.

The method used for the integration of the bridging course is called JITR (Just In Time Review) due to certain similarities with JITT (Just In Time Teaching). Before the next class, the student can take a Moodle quiz having to do with a skill from school

mathematics, such as how to form the equation of a line in preparation for the tangent to the graph of a function at a point. The student receives a grade for the quiz and can review the school topic if necessary. In class, a method for finding the tangent line is presented. The students have already refreshed a necessary component and see their efforts being rewarded during the lecture. Furthermore, the fact that there are fewer questions regarding school mathematics during the lecture, there is more time to spend on the topic at hand.

Two groups of students have been considered: Winter Semester 2023/24 (59 participants) and Winter Semester 24/25 (23 participants), which we will abbreviate as WS 23 and WS 24. Of these students, 35 and 21, respectively, completed identical entry tests dealing with topics from school mathematics. The average student in the earlier year achieved 56% of the points compared to 66% in the latter year.

Below is a list of school topics refreshed needed for the college level topic(s) in the same line. Of the 21 total participants in WS 24, the number of users and the average number of views per student is given for each school topic. Unfortunately, the data from WS 23 is difficult to interpret because the quizzes were contained in two different places, and it was not possible to follow overlap in usage. It can be said that the usage drastically went down at the end of the semester in both years.

School Topic [Participants/Avg. Views]	Calculus Topic
distributive laws [14/6.7]	mathematical induction
factoring polynomials [12/4.5]	mathematical induction
fractions [10/3.7]	number sets, complex numbers
sine and cosine [15/7.1]	complex numbers, polar representation
functional notation [14/4.8]	functions, difference quotient
laws of exponents [12/4.7]	Sequences
roots [8/2.6]	Series
logarithms [6/4]	Continuity
equation of a line [6/5]	Tangent
area [3/3.2]	Integration

Whereas the students felt comfortable with topics such as roots and area, where the average number of views per person was 2.6 and 3.2 respectively, students demonstrated less confidence in topics such as sine and cosine and distributive laws (views per person 7.1 and 6.7 respectively).

In WS 23, 45% of the students did some portion of the quizzes pertaining to school mathematics. This percentage rose to 78% in the next year (WS 24), which can be explained by the fact that time was given at the end of the exercise session for students to begin taking the quiz(zes) during the earlier part of the semester. Unfortunately, the portion of students taking the quizzes drastically decreased for the last several chapters in both years.

Note that the number of students still in attendance at the end of WS 23 was 31 of the original 59 participants (53%). In WS 24, 17 out of 23 (79%) of the students attended class until the end. Integrating the quizzes into the exercise session at the beginning of the semester seems to have been beneficial for class participation throughout the semester.

Clearly, we do not expect the individual examination results to correlate heavily with the school quizzes. For the sake of completion, we note some of the overall results. In WS 23 approximately 51% (WS 24, 78%) of the students completed the examination at the end of the semester, which was similar to class participation at the end of the semester. The average grades of those taking the examination were substantially different (C- in WS 23, B- in WS 24), which was expected since the average entrance test scores were somewhat different (56% vs. 66%). The percentage of students successfully passing the course was 41% in WS 23 compared to 65% in WS 24. The success rates for the exam with respect to those taking the Moodle quizzes for school mathematics were similar: 80% in WS 23 and 83% in WS 24. Thus, students who took the Moodle quizzes were much more likely to continue participating and succeed in the examination. How much of this was due to abilities and motivation is not clear.

Conclusion

The method of Just In Time Review (JITR) was presented in this contribution. Just like its counterpart, Just In Time Teaching, there is a saving in time that can be used in other ways during the lecture. We do not expect our best students to profit as much as the average or below average student. Nothing can replace talent and a solid background in school mathematics. Additionally, there is more to the learning process than just resources and methods. The students who dislike mathematics will generally not become fans by taking a few quizzes. As we saw from the study at the TUB, enjoying mathematics and feeling confident are paramount for success at the tertiary level. Thus, JITR cannot be thought of as a one size fits all type of solution for succeeding in mathematics. It does appear to serve its function as a reminder for the best students and as a wake-up call for others. What students do with that information is up to them. Perhaps requiring additional work if a quiz is not passed would be helpful. The main benefit appears to be increased participation in class, which leads to an increased success rate in the examination.

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